

Prevalence and Factors Associated with Tuberculosis Disease among Community PEOPLE of Budhanilkantha Municipality Bagmati Province Nepal

Mahendra Giri¹, Rajani Bohara², Shailesh Kumar Pandit³, Sandip Rawal⁴ mesh Gautam⁴

¹ Department of Research and Innovation, Innovative Foundation for Health and Research (IFHR), Kathmandu, Nepal

² Department of Healthcare Management, National Open College (NOC), Sanepa, Ringroad, Bagmati Province, Nepal

³ Department of Program and Project, One Step Ahead Foundation (ASAF), Kathmandu, Nepal

⁴ Ministry of Health and Population, Lumbini Provincial Office, Lumbini Province, Nepal

Article Info.	Abstract
<p>Responding Author Mahendr Giri</p> <p>Email mdr.giri21@gmail.com</p> <p>Article History Received: 10 January, 2025 Accepted : 12 May, 2025</p> <p>Cite Giri, M. Bohara, R., Pandit, S. K., & Rawal, S. (2025). Prevalence and factors associated with tuberculosis disease among community People of Budhanilkantha municipality Bagmati province Nepal. <i>Insight Journal of National Open College</i>, 2(1), 81–95. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15366077</p>	<p>Tuberculosis (TB), caused by <i>Mycobacterium tuberculosis</i>, remains a significant public health issue in Nepal, primarily affecting the lungs and spreading via airborne droplets. Overcrowding, poor socioeconomic conditions, and immunocompromised states such as HIV/AIDS and diabetes increase susceptibility to TB infection. This study aimed to assess the prevalence and associated factors of TB among community members in Budanilkantha Municipality. A descriptive cross-sectional design was employed, selecting wards 3, 10, and 12 through random sampling. Data were gathered from 203 respondents using a structured questionnaire via the KOBO Toolbox, following informed consent and municipal approval. Analysis was conducted with IBM SPSS, utilizing descriptive statistics and relevant tests. The mean age of respondents was 41.2 years, with an even gender distribution. TB prevalence was 3.4%, highest among those aged 39–59, but no significant association with sociodemographic factors was found. While 82.8% had heard of TB, only 54.2% understood its transmission. Most respondents (79.3%) had never smoked, though 9.9% were current smokers. Regarding TB testing, 35.5% reported access to multiple facilities, but 23.6% noted limited availability. For healthcare access, 31.5% traveled on foot, and 59.6% required over 30 minutes to reach a DOTS center. Despite high general awareness, knowledge gaps about transmission and limited access to testing persist. Transportation barriers and smoking habits among a minority may hinder TB control. Targeted health education and improved service accessibility are recommended to strengthen TB prevention and care.</p> <p>Keywords: community people, infectious disease, prevalence, TB, tuberculosis</p>

Introduction

Tuberculosis (TB) is a serious illness that mainly affects the lungs. The microorganism that causes tuberculosis is a type of bacteria called *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (Philip C. Hopewell, 2004). A TB infection may be in one of two stages, viz. latent TB infection and active TB. Primary infection is usually followed by the stage called latent TB infection. Immune system cells build a wall around lung tissue with TB germs. The microorganism can't do any more harm if the immune system keeps them under control, but the agent may survive. There are no symptoms during latent TB infection (Adhikari N, 2019). Active TB disease happens when the immune system can't control an infection. Agents cause disease throughout the lungs or other parts of the body. Active TB disease may happen right after primary infection. But it usually happens after months or years of latent TB infection. Symptoms of active TB disease in the lungs usually begin gradually and worsen over a few weeks. They may include coughing for more than 2 weeks, coughing up blood or mucus, chest pain, fever, chills, night sweats, weight loss, not wanting to eat, etc. (Christian Wejse, 2008).

TB can spread when a person with the illness through droplet nuclei, which come from the coughs and sneezes of the TB-infected person and are inhaled by the healthy person (1). Similarly, TB spreads easily where overcrowded. People living with HIV/AIDS and other weakened immune systems have a higher risk of getting infections from TB than people with typical immune systems (Adhikari N, 2019)

Global Tuberculosis Report: Nepal has had a relatively high incidence of TB cases. Efforts have been made to improve case detection and treatment, but challenges such as access to healthcare services in remote areas and the presence of vulnerable populations contribute to the persistence of the disease. School children and elderly people are the more vulnerable groups susceptible to TB infections. The TB control program also planned to create awareness about TB through the active participation of community people (Giorgia Sulis, 2014).

Nepal is a developing country where the majority of the population are living with poor socioeconomic conditions, which is one of the determinants of TB. People facing poorer socio-economic conditions in Nepal are more likely to develop TB. Moreover, tobacco use greatly increases the risk of TB Disease and death. More than 20% Tuberculosis cases worldwide are attributable to smoking (Colin D Mathers, 2006).

The WHO and the United Nations' Millennium Development Goals (MDG), together with the Stop TB Strategy, have developed strategies for eliminating TB, which have led to a decline in the absolute number of TB deaths and the TB incidence rate since the year 2000 (Mukund Uplekar, 2015). Nepal is one of the member states that have committed to these strategies and have made progress regarding TB throughout the last decades. The National Tuberculosis Program (NTP) has been the responsible agency, and, in 1996, the directly observed treatment short-course (DOTS) strategy, a 5-component strategy for TB management and control, was initiated in Nepal. Subsequently, the Stop TB Strategy, The WHO strategy to curb TB by 2015, and the END TB Strategy were adopted (Adhikari N, 2019).

Justification of the Study

Though TB incidence, prevalence and mortality have been observed to have declined over the last decade. However, the elimination of the disease at a global level is still out of reach, and massive resource investment is still required. TB is a poverty-related disease which disproportionately affects the poorest and the most vulnerable and marginalized population groups wherever it occurs. Improving access to diagnosis and care, the basic requirements in the fight against TB, are particularly challenging in these persons. Besides, TB control cannot be carried out without setting up an effective surveillance system in order to define the course of the epidemic and assess the impact of control measures on the disease. Hence, TB national programs must devote significant resources to the disease-specific recording and reporting system (Westaway, 1989)

Despite the existence of the Bacille Calmette-Guérin (BCG) vaccine, which provides partial protection against severe forms of TB in children, there is no highly effective vaccine for adults. TB has significant social and economic implications, affecting individuals, families, and communities. The disease can lead to loss of productivity, economic hardship, and stigmatization (Westaway, 1989).

Objective (s) of the Study

The primary objective of this study was to evaluate the prevalence of TB and its associated factors among community members. Specifically, the study aimed to measure the prevalence of TB and examine the relationship between socio-demographic characteristics and the disease.

Methodology

A descriptive cross-sectional study design was carried out to find out the KAP of TB among community people. The study area was Budhanilkantha Municipality, Bagmati Province, Nepal, which has been planned to be a TB-free municipality in the next 5 years. Therefore, TB disease was given more priority, making it relevant to conduct the research study.

The study population consisted of 127,151 individuals, the total population of the municipality. Ward 10 had a total population of 33,623, Ward 3 had a population of 8,004, and Ward 12 had a population of 19,425. The purposive sampling technique was adopted, and the calculated sample size was 203 for this study.

Community members aged 18 years or above, all family members above 18 years of TB patients, and individuals with or without a personal history of tuberculosis were included for this study.

Dependent variables, prevalence of TB, and independent variables such as age, sex, family type, ethnicity, education status of parents, main occupation, monthly family income, history of illness, smoking, alcohol intake, and accessibility of DOTS centers were considered in the study.

A self-prepared questionnaire was developed in the KOBO Toolbox platform, and a face-to-face interview technique was adopted to gather information from the respondents. Data protection was done to safeguard and secure information from unauthorized access, disclosure, alteration, and destruction. To ensure proper data protection, data collected from the respondents was kept safely with password protection, and the data was not shared with anyone except the supervisor. In order to ensure ethical

consideration, approval letters were taken from the Department of Public Health. Written permission was taken from respondents. All information obtained was used only for study. Privacy and confidentiality of collected data were maintained. The right of the respondent was highly respected.

After examining the data, it was entered in SPSS for data management and analysis. The data analysis was done by calculating the descriptive statistics like mean, chi-square test, Fisher’s exact test and standard deviation for required independent variables which is widely followed by Mishra, A.K., Sudarsan, J.S. & Nithiyanantham, S. (2023: 2025)

Results

In order to illustrate the interpretation, the analyzed data was presented in the table form to meet the objective of the study.

Socio- Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Out of 203, the mean age of the respondents was 41.18 years (SD 11.669). The study showed that the majority of the respondents were ages 39-59 years, i.e., 105 (51.7%); 85 (41.9%) were ages 18-38 years, and 13 (6.4%) were ages 60-80 years. Similarly, there were equal numbers of the male and female respondents, followed by male 101 (49.8%) and female 102 (50.2%). Most of the respondents were Brahmin/Chhetri (125, 61.6%), followed by Janajati (50, 24.6%), Dalit (17, 8.4%), and Madhesi (8, 3.9%). Among the respondents who follow Hinduism, religion is high, i.e., 173 (85.2%), followed by Buddhism 24 (11.8%), Muslim 2 (1%), and Christian 4 (2%). Among the respondents, 166 (81.8%) were married and 24 (11.8%) were non-married. The majority of individuals came from nuclear families, 140 (68.96%); followed by joint families, 59 (29.06%); and extended families, 4 (1.9%). Among the participants, 10 individuals were government employees, accounting for 4.9% of the total sample. Non-government employees represented a significant portion of the study, with 46 individuals making up 22.7%. The agricultural sector had a minimal presence with only 2 participants, constituting 1% of the total. Business professionals were the largest group, with 51 individuals, or 25%. Health workers comprised 3.9% of the sample, with 8 participants. Housewives formed a notable segment, with 34 individuals making up 16.7%. Students also had a significant representation, with 42 participants accounting for 20.7%. Lastly, those categorized under 'Others', which included foreign employment, numbered 10, making up 4.9% of the total participants. Most of the respondents fall within the 400,000 to 699,000 income range, 105 (51.7%); followed by the 100,000 to 399,000 range, 76 (37.4%); and the 700,000 to 999,000 range, 22 (10.8%).

Table 1
Socio- demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Variables	Frequency (N=203)	Percentage (%)
Age	(in	years)
18-38	85	41.9%
39-59	105	51.7%
60-80	13	6.4%
Mean 41.18± SD 11.669		

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Variables	Frequency (N=203)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	101	49.8%
Female	102	50.2%
Ethnicity		
Brahmin/Chhetri	125	61.6%
Janajati	50	24.6%
Dalit	17	8.4%
Madhesi	8	3.9%
Others(Thakuri)	3	1.5%
Religion		
Hinduism	173	85.2%
Buddhism	24	11.8%
Muslim	2	1%
Christian	4	2%
Marital Status		
Married	166	81.8%
Unmarried	24	11.8%
Divorced	7	3.4%
Widow/widower	5	2.5%
Separated	1	0.5%
Family Size		
Nuclear	140	68.96%
Joint	59	29.06%
Extended	4	1.9%
Occupation		
Government employee	10	4.9%
Non-government employee	46	22.7%
Agriculture	2	1%
Business	51	25%
Health worker	8	3.9%
House wife	34	16.7%
Student	42	20.7%
Others (Foreign employment)	10	4.9%

Variables	Frequency (N=203)	Percentage (%)
Annual Income		
100000 to 399000	76	37.4%
400000 to 699000	105	51.7%
700000 to 999000	22	10.8%
Mean 481534.98±	SD	365404.80

Personal Factors related Characteristics

Table 2 represents the prevalence of TB infection was found to be relatively low, with only 7 individuals (3.4%) reporting a positive TB status, while the majority, 196 individuals (96.6%), reported not being infected. Among those infected, the majority 6 (85.7%) had been diagnosed less than six months prior to the study, whereas 1 (14.3%) was diagnosed more than six months. When it came to seeking treatment, 4 (57.1%) of the TB patients visited health posts, while the remaining 3 (42.9%) had been seeking treatment from hospital.

All TB-infected individuals 7(100%) reported experienced a cough lasting more than two weeks. Other symptoms reported included fever 2(28.6%), weight loss 5(71.4%), and anorexia 1(14.3%). In terms of their experience within society, 14.3% of TB patients experienced stigma or discrimination, 71.4% received support, and 14.3% reported no significant social impact. Regarding pre-existing medical conditions, 40 individuals (19.7%) indicated they had such conditions, 146 individuals (71.9%) did not, and 17 individuals (8.4%) were unsure.

In terms of exposure to TB, 19 individuals (9.4%) had close contact with a TB patient, whereas 184 individuals (90.6%) had not. Additionally, 12 individuals (5.9%) reported having travelled or lived in areas with a high prevalence of TB, while 191 individuals (94.1%) had not. Awareness of the Bacillus Calmette-Guérin (BCG) vaccine, which provides protection against TB, was moderate, with 106 individuals (52.2%) being aware, 47 individuals (23.2%) not aware, and 50 individuals (24.6%) unsure. When it came to having received the BCG vaccine, 117 individuals (57.6%) confirmed they had been vaccinated, whereas 86 individuals (42.4%) had not. Furthermore, 138 individuals (68%) reported taking preventive measures against TB, while 65 individuals (32%) indicated they were not taking any preventive measures.

Table 2

Personal Factors Characteristics

Infected with TB	Frequency (N=203)	Percentage (%)
Yes	7	3.4%
No	196	96.6%
If Yes (n=7), Time Duration		
Less than 6 months	6	85.7%
More than 6 months	1	14.3%
Seeking Treatment (n=7)		

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Infected with TB	Frequency (N=203)	Percentage (%)
Health Post	4	57.1%
More than 6 months	3	42.9%
Symptoms experienced (n=7)		
Cough more than 2 weeks		
Yes	7	100%
No	0	
Fever		
Yes	2	28.6%
No	5	71.4%
Weight Loss		
Yes	5	71.4%
No	2	28.6%
Anorexia		
Yes	1	14.3%
No	6	85.7%
Experience in society		
Stigma/discrimination	1	14.3%
Support	5	71.4%
Nothing	1	14.3%
Pre-existing medical conditions		
Yes	40	19.7%
No	146	71.9%
Not sure 17 8.4%		
Close contact with TB patient		
Yes	19	9.4%
No	184	90.6%
Travelled or lived in areas of High TB prevalence		
Yes	12	5.9%
No	191	94.1%
Aware of BCG vaccine		
Yes	106	52.2%
No	47	23.2%

Infected with TB	Frequency (N=203)	Percentage (%)
Not sure 50 24.6%		
Received BCG vaccine		
Yes	117	57.6%
No	86	42.4%
Taking preventive measures		
Yes	138	68%
No	65	32%

Knowledge related Characteristics

Table 3 indicates that the majority, 168 individuals (82.8%), had heard about tuberculosis (TB), while 35 individuals (17.2%) had not aware about it. Among the 168 individuals who were aware of TB, various sources of information were cited. Health personnel or Female Community Health Volunteers (FCHV) were a source of information for 79 respondents, accounting for 47% of those aware of TB. TV and radio were the most frequently mentioned sources, reported by 105 respondents, or 62.5%. Magazines and newspapers were cited by 26 respondents, making up 15.5%. Information from female friends was reported by 42 respondents (25%), while internet webpages were mentioned by 83 respondents, also 25%. Courses or formal lectures were a source of information for 25 respondents, or 15.5%. Additionally, 6 respondents (25%) indicated they had received information from all of the sources.

Knowledge about TB transmission was present in 110 individuals (54.2%), whereas 93 individuals (45.8%) did not know how TB is transmitted. Regarding the cause of TB, 100 individuals (49.3%) correctly identified it as being caused by germs or bacteria, 45 individuals (22.2%) did not, and 58 individuals (28.6%) were unsure.

When it comes to recognizing the main symptoms of TB, such as a cough lasting more than two weeks, chest pain, and sweating, 145 individuals (71.4%) were aware, 9 individuals (4.4%) were not, and 49 individuals (24.1%) were unsure. In terms of prevention, 134 individuals (66%) knew that TB could be prevented by covering the mouth and nose during coughing and sneezing, while 29 individuals (14.3%) did not, and 40 individuals (19.7%) were unsure. Additionally, 112 individuals (55.2%) believed that TB could be prevented by not sharing utensils, while 91 individuals (44.8%) did not share this belief.

Knowledge about TB diagnosis was less prevalent, with only 84 individuals (41.4%) knowing how TB is diagnosed, compared to 119 individuals (58.6%) who did not. Among those who knew how TB is diagnosed (N=84), 23 individuals (27.4%) mentioned chest X-rays, 46 individuals (54.8%) cited sputum tests, and 15 individuals (17.9%) referred to blood tests.

Table 3*Knowledge related Characteristics*

Variables	Frequency (N=203)	Percentage (%)
Heard about TB		
Yes	168	82.8%
No	35	17.2%
If Yes, from where		
Health personnel/FCHV 79	47%	
TV, Radio	105	62.5%
Magazine, Newspaper 26	15.5%	
Female Friends 42	25%	
Internet webpage 83	25%	
Course/formal lecture 25	15.5%	
All of the above 6	25%	
*Multiple Responses		
Known how TB is transmitted		
Yes	110	54.2%
No	93	45.8%
Caused by germ/bacteria		
Yes	100	49.3%
No	45	22.2%
Don't Know	58	28.6%
Main symptoms are cough>2weeks, chest pain, sweating		
Yes	145	71.4%
No	9	4.4%
Not sure	49	24.1%
TB can be prevented by covering mouth, nose during coughing and sneezing		
Yes	134	66%

Variables	Frequency (N=203)	Percentage (%)
No	29	14.3%
Not sure	40	19.7%
Can be prevented by not sharing utensils		
Yes	112	55.2%
No	91	44.8%
Know how TB is diagnosed		
Yes	84	41.4%
No	119	58.6%
If yes (n=84)		
Chest X-ray	23	27.4%
Sputum Test	46	54.8%
Blood Test	15	17.9%

Risk Factors related Characteristics

Table 4 indicates the practice of smoking by respondents. The majority of respondents, 161 individuals (79.3%) reported that they had never smoked. On the other hand, 20 respondents (9.9%) indicated that they have still been smoking and 22 respondents (10.8%) had smoked in the past. Similarly, less than 10 sticks smoked per day were a bit higher i.e. 11 respondents (55%) and more than 10 sticks were 9 respondents (i.e. 45%). Moreover, among the respondents most of the respondents i.e. 153 (75.4%) had never drink alcohol while 18 respondents (33.1%) drinks frequently and 32 respondent drinks sometimes. Meanwhile, 23(i.e. 11.3%) of respondents have immune-compromised disease, 155(i.e. 76.4%) respondents didn't have immune-compromised disease while 25(i.e. 12.3%) respondents were not sure about it. Furthermore, the maximum number of respondents i.e. 172 respondents (84.7%) didn't have family history of TB, 12 respondents had family history of TB whereas 19 respondents were not sure about their family history of TB.

Table 1

Risk Factor related Characteristics

Variables	Frequency (N=203)	Percentage (%)
Smoking		
Yes (currently)	20	9.9%
Yes (in the past)	22	10.8%
No	161	79.3%
Number of sticks smoke per day (n=20)		

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Variables	Frequency (N=203)	Percentage (%)
Less than 10 sticks	11	55%
More than 10 sticks	9	45%
Alcohol consumption		
Yes	18	8.9%
No	153	75.4%
Sometimes	32	15.8%
Immune-compromised disease		
Yes	23	11.3%
No	155	76.4%
Not sure	25	12.3%
Family History of TB		
Yes	12	5.9%
No	172	84.7%
Not sure	19	9.4%

Health system factors related characteristics

Table 5 provides insight into various factors affecting tuberculosis (TB) prevalence and response. It reveals that 72 respondents (i.e. 35.5%) reported the availability of multiple TB testing facilities, while 51 respondents (i.e. 25.1%) noted only one accessible location. Limited availability of testing facilities was reported by 48 respondents (i.e. 23.6%) and 32 respondents (15.8%) were unsure about the availability. Regarding transportation to healthcare facilities, 64 (31.5%) of individuals travelled on foot, 61 (30%) used buses, 59 (29.1%) utilized their own vehicles, and 19 (9.4%) of respondents relied on taxis. Similarly, the time taken to reach DOTS centre was less than 30 minutes for 121 (59.6%) of respondents, while 82 (40.4%) took more than 30 minutes.

Furthermore, the knowledge level of health workers about TB varied, with 44 (21.7%) being very knowledgeable and 122 (60.1%) somewhat knowledgeable. However, 31 (15.3%) of health workers were not very knowledgeable, and 6 (3%) had no knowledge at all. Community efforts towards TB prevention were acknowledged by 55 of respondents (i.e.27.1%), while 84 (41.4%) denied such efforts, and 64 (31.5%) were uncertain. Moreover, government support for TB initiatives was perceived as strong by 30 respondents (14.8%), moderate by 95 (46.8%), limited by 58 (28.6%) respondents, and non-existent by 20 (i.e. 9.9%).

Table 2

Health System related Characteristics

Variables	Frequency (N=203)	Percentage (%)
Easily accessible TB testing facilities		
Yes, multiple locations	72	35.5%
Yes, one location	51	25.1%
No, limited availability 48	23.6%	
Not sure	32	15.8%
Means of transportation to reach HF		
By taxi	19	9.4%
On foot	64	31.5%
By bus	61	30%
Own Vehicle	59	29.1%
Time to reach DOTS centre		
Less than 30 minutes	121	59.6%
More than 30 minutes	82	40.4%
Knowledge about TB (For Health worker)		
Very Knowledgeable	44	21.7%
Somewhat Knowledgeable	122	60.1%
Not very knowledgeable 31	15.3%	
Not knowledgeable at all	6	3%
Community efforts about TB prevention		
Yes	55	27.1%
No	84	41.4%
Not sure	64	31.5%
Government support		
Strong support 30	14.8%	
Moderate support	95	46.8%
Limited support 58	28.6%	
No support	20	9.9%

Discussion

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among 203 community people of Budhanilkantha municipality with an objective to find out the prevalence and associated factors of TB among community people. The present study showed that the 3.4% of TB prevalence in the community where the study was conducted in Ethiopia assessed a 7.8% prevalence rate of TB infection, which is more than two times higher than the prevalence rate in Nepal (Abinet Adane, 2020). Likewise, an institution-based cross-sectional study conducted between March and August 2018 among people living with HIV in Nepal found that the median age of the participants was 36 (30–43) years (Nilaramba Adhikari, 2022).

The study shows that majority (82.8%) had heard about the TB infection, where only more than half (54.2%) were aware of its mode of transmission. A similar national and subnational study had been conducted in Nepal showed that people who have completed secondary or higher education have more than five times higher odds of being well informed about TB compared to those without any formal education (Yoko Iwaki, 2021).

Present study found that there were no significant association was observed with sociodemographic characteristics. However, a study conducted National Tuberculosis Center (NTC), Bhaktapur, Nepal found that socio demographic risk factors can contribute to the development of TB in human beings (Tulsi Ram Gompo, 2020).

A study found that nearly two-thirds (59.6%) reported that accessing a DOTS center took more than 30 minutes by walking or vehicle transportation, whereas 40.4% said that it took less than 30 minutes to reach services. A qualitative study conducted in central and western regions of Nepal found that access to health centers for the majority of the population is often neglected. Similarly, in mountainous villages with sparse settlements spread over vast areas, reaching health centers poses a considerable challenge (Sujuan Babu Marahatta, 2020).

Conclusion

This study among 203 community members in Budhanilkantha municipality found a TB prevalence of 3.4%, which is notably lower than the 7.8% reported in Ethiopia and the 9.9% among people living with HIV in Nepal. The mean age of respondents was 41.18 years, with an almost equal gender distribution. While general awareness of TB was high (82.8%), only just over half (54.2%) understood its mode of transmission, echoing national findings that education level and socioeconomic status significantly influence TB awareness and knowledge in Nepal.

Despite the lack of significant associations between sociodemographic factors and TB prevalence in this study, other research from Nepal highlights that factors such as age, gender, ethnic background, and HIV status can play a critical role in TB risk. Moreover, environmental and geographic determinants—such as land surface temperature, urbanization, and precipitation—have been shown to significantly influence TB prevalence across Nepal, with higher rates clustering in densely populated and socioeconomically disadvantaged districts. These findings underscore the importance of integrating environmental and spatial analyses into TB control strategies.

Access to TB services remains a challenge: nearly 60% of respondents reported needing more than 30 minutes to reach a DOTS center, consistent with qualitative studies highlighting geographic and infrastructural barriers in rural and mountainous regions. Stigma, fear of diagnosis, and limited healthcare accessibility further impede timely diagnosis and treatment, contributing to ongoing transmission and delayed care-seeking.

In summary, while this study demonstrates relatively high TB awareness, significant gaps persist in knowledge of transmission and accessibility to diagnostic and treatment facilities. The findings reinforce the need for targeted, locally adapted health education initiatives, improved service delivery, and the integration of environmental and socioeconomic considerations into public health planning. Addressing these multifaceted barriers is essential for reducing TB burden, achieving earlier diagnosis and treatment, and ultimately advancing TB control efforts in Nepal

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Author Contributions

Mahendra Giri and Rajani Bohara conceptualized the research ideas, while Sandip Rawal, Shailes Kumar Pandit, and Umesh Gautam oversaw the field activities, including securing permission and conducting data collection. Subsequently, Mahendra Giri, Umesh Gautam, and Rajani Bohara analyzed the data and prepared the manuscript for publication.

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interests among authors for the publication.

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